

Simultaneous first derivative spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) using 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone

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Abstract : The reagent, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone (PPDOT) has been used for the determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} by spectrophotometric method. The reagent gives intense colour reactions with copper(II) and nickel(II) in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer medium. Maximum colour intensity is observed in the pH range 3.0-8.0. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the methods for the determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) are 0.575×10^4 , 1.20×10^4 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.0118 and 0.00503 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The compositions of copper and nickel complexes of PPDOT as determined by Job's and molar ratio methods are found to be 1 : 2 (M : L). First derivative methods have been developed for the determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}. Simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} carried out by measuring the peak-base line technique at 500 and 467.5 nm respectively. The method is carried out without the need for employing simultaneous equations in the determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} in synthetic mixtures and in edible oils and seeds.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, thiosemicarbazone, copper(II), nickel(II).

Oximes and thiosemicarbazones are widely employed for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions¹. However, reagents containing both functional groups are not exploited much in the derivative spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. In continuation of previous work², herein we report, first derivative spectrophotometric methods for the determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) using novel reagent viz. 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone (PPDOT) in aqueous medium. The first derivative spectra of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes with PPDOT show maximum amplitudes at 500 and 425 nm respectively in the pH range 3.0-8.0. However, nickel complex has measurable amplitude at 467.5 nm where copper complex has zero amplitude. Therefore this wavelength is chosen for the determination of nickel. The metal ions i.e. Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} have been determined simultaneously by measuring the amplitudes at 500 and 467.5 nm respectively. The method is applied for the determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) in real and synthetic samples.

Results and discussion

The reagent, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone (1) is a blend of two important functional groups viz. oxime and thiosemicarbazone. Novel

types of reagents viz. oxime-thiosemicarbazones are not exploited much for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. Moreover the derivative methods using this class of reagents are scarce.

The deprotonation constants of PPDOT have been determined by recording UV-Visible spectra at different pH values³. The bathochromic shift of strong absorption band of PPDOT in solution from 290 to 300 nm indicates that in solution on increasing pH, the acid (=N-OH → =N-O⁻ + H⁺) is neutralized and >C=S group is enolized and dissociated. The values of the deprotonation of PPDOT were found to be 6.53 (pK₁) and 8.55 (pK₂). The pK₁ may be assigned to deprotonation of imine (NH) through enolization while pK₂ is assigned to deprotonation of oxime hydrogen (=N-OH).

Important physicochemical and analytical properties of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of PPDOT are summarized in Table 1. The colour reactions between the metal ions and PPDOT are instantaneous at RT. The absorbances of complexes were found to be constant for more than 24 h. Maximum colour intensity is observed for both complexes over a wide range of pH (Table 1). The order of addition of buffer, metal ions [Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}] and reagent has no adverse effect on the absorbance of complexes.

Table 1. Important physicochemical and analytical properties of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of PPDOT

Sl. no.	Characteristics	Cu-PPDOT	Ni-PPDOT
1.	Absorption maximum (λ_{\max} , nm)	465	395
2.	pH-range (optimum)	3.0-8.0	3.0-6.0
3.	Mole of reagent required per mole of metal ion for full colour development	5-fold	10
4.	Time stability of the complex (in h)	24	24
5.	Molar absorptivity (lit mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	0.58×10^4	1.2×10^4
6.	Sandell's sensitivity (μg of metal cm ⁻²)	0.0110	0.0050
7.	Specific absorptivity (ml g ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	0.091	0.204
8.	Beer's law validity range ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, or ppm)	0.763-7.63	0.9-3.76
9.	Optimum concentration range from Ringbom plots ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$)	1.25-4.76	1.9-3.76
10.	Composition of the complex as obtained in Job's and molar ratio methods	1 : 2	1 : 2
11.	Stability constant of the complex from Job's curve	8.25×10^7	5.15×10^9
12.	Standard deviation	0.0117 ^a	0.0048 ^b

^aIn ten replicate determinations of 2.54 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of Cu^{II}.

^bIn ten replicate determinations of 0.94 mg/ml of Ni^{II}.

Derivative spectra of Cu^{II}-PPDOT and Ni^{II}-PPDOT complexes :

The zero-order spectrum of metal complexes with PPDOT were recorded in the wavelength region 350-600 nm against reagent blank. The zero-order spectra of solutions of copper-PPDOT (curve a) and nickel-PPDOT (curve b) complexes in an aqueous acidic buffer medium (pH 6) are shown in Fig. 1. The absorption spectra of the complexes overlap considerably and therefore direct spectrophotometric determination of one metal in the presence of another is not possible. From the zero-order spectrum first derivative spectra were recorded from which analytical wavelengths are ascertained. The first derivative spectra of complexes are also shown in Fig. 1 (curves a' and b'). The derivative spectra indicates that at 467.5

nm copper complexes has zero amplitude while nickel complex has measurable amplitude. The amplitude of nickel(II) complex at 500 nm is found to be 0.34 times to that of its amplitude at 467.5 nm where Cu^{II} has zero amplitude. The amplitude at 467.5 nm corresponds to that nickel(II) only.

Hence it can be determined directly. On the other hand, copper(II) can be determined by measuring its amplitude at 500 nm using the following expression.

$$A_{500}^{\text{Cu}} = A_{500}^{\text{Mix}} - (A_{467.5}^{\text{Mix}} \times 0.34)$$

$$A_{500}^{\text{Ni}} = \text{Amplitude of the mixture containing Cu}^{\text{II}} \text{ and Ni}^{\text{II}} \text{ at 500 nm.}$$

Mix

$A_{467.5}$ = Amplitude of the mixture containing Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} at 467.5 nm.

Cu

A_{500} = Amplitude of the mixture containing Cu^{II} only at 500 nm.

Typical spectra are shown in Fig. 2.

Calibration plots were constructed at 467.5 nm for Ni^{II} and 500 nm for Cu^{II} by plotting the derivative amplitudes against the amounts of nickel(II) respectively.

The plots are linear obeying the relationship.

$$A_{500} = 0.0309C - 0.0004$$

$$A_{467.5} = 0.0089C + 0.0008$$

for copper(II) at 500 nm and for nickel(II) at 467.5 nm.

It was noticed from the linear plots that the derivative amplitude was proportional to the concentration of the metal ions in the range of 0.700–7.638 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Cu^{II} and in the range of 0.400–4.50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ni^{II} at both 467.5 nm and 500 nm respectively.

The effect of foreign ions was studied to know the selectivity of the derivative methods. The amount of foreign ion, which brings about change in the amplitude by $\pm 2\%$ was taken as the tolerance limit. Interference of various ions was studied with 3.8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of copper(II) and 1.9 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of nickel(II). The results are given in Table 2.

It is noticed that all the ions that do not interfere in the zero-order determination of metal ions also do not interfere in the first derivative analyses. The tolerance limit values, in general are higher in the first derivative methods than those in the zero-order determination of metal ions. For example, nickel(II) which interferes in the zero-order and is tolerable 3-fold in the first order method.

Applications :

The simultaneous first derivative spectrometric determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) in synthetic mixtures were carried out by employing the recommended procedure. The results are presented in Table 3. The results obtained in the analysis of edible oils and seeds are presented in Table 4.

Fig. 1. Zero-order and first-order derivative spectra of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} : (a) zero-order spectrum of Cu^{II} -PPDOT [$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} = 4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ and $\text{PPDOT} = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$]; (a') first-order derivative spectrum of Cu^{II} -PPDOT system [$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} = 9.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ and $\text{PPDOT} = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$]; (b) zero-order spectrum of Ni^{II} -PPDOT system [$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} = 4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ and $\text{PPDOT} = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$]; (b') first derivative spectrum of Ni^{II} -PPDOT system [$\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} = 6.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ and $\text{PPDOT} = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$].

Fig. 2. First derivative of (a) Cu^{II}-PPDOT system and (b) Ni^{II}-PPDOT system [Cu^{II} = 9.6 × 10⁻⁵ M; Ni^{II} = 6.4 × 10⁻⁵ M and PPDOT = 4 × 10⁻⁴ M].

Table 2. Tolerance limit of foreign ions

Sl. no.	Ion added	Tolerance limit (µg/ml)	
		Copper(II)	Nickel(II)
1.	Citrate	2270	1515
2.	Iodate	1910	1530
3.	Tartrate	1775	1185
4.	Iodate	1525	1525
5.	Thiosulphate	1345	900
6.	Sulphate	1155	770
7.	Phosphate	1140	760
8.	Bromide	960	960
9.	Thiourea	760	610
10.	Nitrate	745	495
11.	Ascorbate	700	70
12.	Thiocyanate	695	465
13.	Oxalate	530	705
14.	Chloride	425	425
15.	Fluoride	230	230
16.	Tungsten(VI)	370	220
17.	Molybdenum(VI)	155	16
18.	Cadmium(II)	135	-
19.	Aluminum(III)	110	325
20.	Manganese(II)	5	65 (65)
21.	Chromium(III)	45 (30)	20 (2.1)
22.	Iron(III)	36 (25)	96
23.	Zinc(II)	2.4 (0.8)	6.5
24.	Cobal(II)	2.1 (0.6)	3.0

Table-2 (contd.)

25.	Vanadium(V)	0.7 (0.6)	3.0 (0.6)
26.	Silver(I)	2.0 (0.7)	1.3
27.	Copper(II)	-	50 ^b (1.5)
28.	Nickel(II)	11.5 ^a (0.1)	-

(-) Seriously interferes.

^aDetermination carried out 467.5 nm.

^bDetermination is carried out at 500 nm (peak-zero method).

Tolerance limit values in parenthesis correspond to zero-order method illustrating the advantage of derivative methods.

Table 3. Simultaneous determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} in synthetic mixtures

Taken (µg/ml)		Found ^a (µg/ml)		Error (%)	
Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}
2.288	0.939	2.268	0.918	-0.9	-2.2
2.288	1.409	2.233	1.410	-2.4	+0.1
2.288	1.878	2.246	1.826	-1.8	-2.8
2.288	2.348	2.198	2.369	-3.9	+0.9
2.288	2.817	2.249	2.817	-1.7	-
2.288	3.756	2.208	3.810	-3.5	+1.6
1.525	1.409	1.537	1.461	+0.8	+3.7
3.050	1.409	3.121	1.404	+2.3	-0.3
4.575	1.409	4.595	1.409	+0.4	-
5.338	1.409	5.424	1.461	+1.6	+3.7

^aAverage of three determinations.

Table 4. Analysis of edible oils and seeds

Sample	Amount found* ($\mu\text{g/g}$)		Amount recovered ^b		Recovery ^c (%)	
	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}
Sesame seed	11.64 (11.74) ^a	- (0.280) ^a	12.41	1.26	97.6	98.4
Ground nut seed	4.50 (4.44)	- (0.07) ^a	5.35	1.20	98.3	112.1
Sesame oil	1.25 (1.29)	- (0.09) ^a	2.25	1.07	98.2	98.1
Sunflower oil	0.67 (0.65) ^a	- (0.08) ^a	1.60	1.10	96.9	101.8
Hydrogenated vegetable oil	- (0.03) ^a	0.12 (0.13) ^a	1.10	1.11	106.8	98.2
Chocolate (Eclairs)	0.97 (0.99) ^a	0.19 (0.18) ^a	1.97	1.17	98.9	99.1

*Average of three determinations.

^aAAS values are given in parenthesis.

^bStandard addition method (1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ each of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were added to the sample).

^cRecovery values were calculated based on AAS data.

Experimental

Schimidzu 160 A microcomputer based UV visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cells was used for all absorbance and amplitude measurements in derivative spectrophotometry. An ELICO LI-120 digital pH meter was used in pH adjustments. All the reagents used were of A.R. grade unless otherwise stated. All solutions were prepared with distilled water. Stock solutions (0.01 M) of copper(II) and nickel(II) were prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of cupric sulphate and nickel ammonium sulphate in 250 ml distilled water respectively. The stock solutions were standardized⁴ and suitably diluted to obtain working solutions of metal ions.

The reagent, 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime thiosemicarbazone (PPDOT) was synthesized by refluxing equimolar solutions of 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione-2-oxime and thiosemicarbazide in 1% HCl-ethanol medium. The reagent solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 236 mg of the compound in 100 ml of dimethylformamide and the solution was found to be stable for one day only. Hydrochloric acid (1 M)-sodium acetate (1 M) (pH 0.5–3.5); sodium acetate (0.2 M)-acetic acid (0.2 M) (pH 4.0–6.5) and ammonium chloride (2 M)-ammonium hydroxide (2 M) (pH 7.0–10.5) were used in the present study.

Recommended procedure :

(a) Determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) (first-

order) :

An aliquot of the solution containing copper(II) or nickel(II) in the analytical concentration range (Cu, 0.763–6.104; Ni, 0.470–3.760 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), 10 ml of buffer solution (pH 5.0), and 1 ml of 0.01 M PPDOT solution were mixed in a 25-ml standard flask and the reaction mixture was diluted to the mark with distilled water. The first derivative spectra of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with PPDOT complexes were recorded. The peak height (*h*) method was followed for the determination of metal ions. The peak height at 500 nm and 467.5 nm is proportional to the concentration of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} respectively. Therefore, peak height method was employed for the construction of calibration plots.

(b) Simultaneous first derivative spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} :

An aliquot of solution containing Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} in the optimum concentration range, 10 ml of buffer solution (pH 4.5) and 1 ml 0.01 M PPDOT solution were mixed in 25-ml standard flask and the reaction mixture was made upto the mark with distilled water. The first derivative amplitude was measured at 500 nm and 467.5 nm and the amounts of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were computed from calibration graphs.

(c) Analysis of edible oils and seeds :

Sample solution of edible oils, seeds and chocolate

were prepared by following the literature procedure⁵. A 50 g of the sample was heated in a 500 conical flask with 40 ml of concentrated HNO₃ on a steam bath and shaken vigorously until a fine emulsion was formed. The heating was continued with gradual addition of 20 ml of conc. HNO₃ and 20 ml of 6% H₂O₂. The combined extracts were evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of HCl and transferred into a 50-ml standard flask quantitatively. The contents were diluted to the mark distilled water.

To 10 ml of buffer (pH 5.0) solution, 1 ml of 0.1 M NaF (to mask iron(III), the sample solution), 2.5 ml of DMF and 1 ml of 0.01 M reagent solution were added. The solution was diluted to volume (25 ml) with distilled water and the first derivative spectra were recorded. The peak heights at 500 and 467.5 nm is measured for the determination of copper and nickel respectively. The amplitudes were referred to the calibration plots and the amounts of copper and nickel were determined. The results including recovery data are given in Table 4.

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